

ICSU World Data System Annual Report 2015–16

Prepared by the WDS International Programme Office

Trusted Data Services for Global Science

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ICSU World Data System
Annual Report 2015–16

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WDS Strategic Targets 2014–2018

1. Make trusted data services an integral part of international collaborative scientific research
2. Nurture active disciplinary and multidisciplinary scientific data services communities
3. Improve the funding environment
4. Improve the trust in and quality of open Scientific Data Services
5. Position ICSU-WDS as the premium global multidisciplinary network for quality-assessed scientific research data

Introduction

The mission of the ICSU World Data System (ICSU-WDS) is to promote long-term stewardship of, and universal and equitable access to, quality-assured scientific data and data services, products, and information across a range of disciplines in the natural and social sciences, and the humanities. ICSU-WDS aims to facilitate scientific research under the International Council for Science's (ICSU's) umbrella by coordinating and supporting trusted scientific data services for the provision, use, and preservation of relevant datasets, while strengthening their links with the research community. WDS was established by ICSU in 2009, building on the recognized legacy of its World Data Centres and Federation of Astronomical and Geophysical data analysis Services.

2015–2016 in Brief

This has been an exciting year for ICSU-WDS, with not only the appointment of a new Scientific Committee (WDS-SC) but also the renewal of the agreement between ICSU and the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology for the latter to host the WDS International Programme Office for a further five years.

The third WDS-SC was appointed in July 2015 for a three-year period, with Prof Sandy Harrison agreeing to be the new SC Chair until 2017. Two further members joined in December to give a full contingent including nine new members. One of the first tasks of the new WDS-SC was to adopt a set of Data Sharing Principles to advance WDS goals and to embody the spirit of Open Science.

The WDS Publishing Data and Certification Working Groups (WGs) presented their final outputs at the Sixth and Seventh Plenary Meetings of the Research Data Alliance, some of which will be taken forward by the Global Science Forum of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. An outcome of major significance from the Publishing Data

WGs was the Open and Universal Data–Literature Interlinking Service—a freely accessible, web-based service that enables users to identify associations between datasets and articles. Furthermore, the Common Requirements and Procedures developed by the Certification WG will be adopted by ICSU-WDS and the Data Seal of Approval over the coming year.

ICSU-WDS co-organized two events in 2015. A joint Workshop with the Scientific Committee on Solar–Terrestrial Physics resulted in the signing of a Letter of Agreement between the two organizations; while over 110 data managers, scientists, funders, and indigenous people gathered at the Second International Polar Data Forum to look at maximizing the value of polar data in solving global challenges. The WDS Webinar series also continued with aplomb, building its reputation through five high-calibre presentations given by leading experts.

Finally, our congratulations go out to Dr Yaxing Wei, who was selected by the WDS-SC as the winner of the WDS Data Stewardship Award for 2015.

Message from the Executive Director

A milestone during the 2015–2016 period was the renewal of the agreement to host the WDS International Programme Office (IPO) in Tokyo for five more years at the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT) of Japan. The agreement was concluded between NICT and the International Council for Science in Paris on 21 September 2015. The generous support provided by NICT during the five years since the establishment of the IPO has been unflinching, and we are grateful for this renewed commitment of support. An event organized in April 2016 in Tokyo to celebrate the renewal of the agreement provided also an opportunity to reflect both on WDS' past achievements and the future challenges facing the programme as it moves forward to expand its membership and realize its objectives.

Considerable progress was made on many fronts over last year! This can be evidenced through the activities and deliverables of several Working Groups (WGs), which are essential components to help WDS deliver on its Strategic Plan. WDS certification was improved and aligned with the Data Seal of Approval thanks to the WDS Certification WG and the Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG under the Research Data Alliance. These important activities will lead to the implementation of a Common

Certification framework that will do much to build a truly universal 'community of excellence' for scientific data services. Other noteworthy achievements are in the area of data publication where, in partnership with WDS Members, science publishers, and the data community at large, we are working to promote building blocks of the global research data infrastructure such as the Scholix Framework and the Data–Literature Interlinking Service. Progress has also been made, through the Knowledge Network WG, on developing a Catalogue of Common Requirements to facilitate interrogation of repository data holdings.

WDS continues to grow and now has 95 Member Organizations, together forming an unprecedented network of *trusted data repositories and services*. We look forward to engaging our Members further into existing WDS activities, and I personally look forward to the discussions that will take place at the next Members' Forum to be held in Denver prior to SciDataCon this coming September.

Mustapha Mokrane
Executive Director, WDS

Message from the Chair

The renewal of the Scientific Committee (SC) in 2015 marks the beginning of a new phase in the life of WDS, focussing on broadening our engagement with data organizations across the full range of scientific domains in order to fulfil our role of promoting 'Trusted Data Services for Global Science'. The foundations for this expansion were laid down by the Committee during the first six years of WDS, under the guidance of the former SC Chair, Bernard Minster. I would like to express our immense gratitude for this pioneering work—mere words are inadequate to describe their huge contribution. However, WDS is extremely fortunate to have a new, diverse and enthusiastic SC—as attested by their Blog posts on the WDS website—to continue with the good work and for this I am also very grateful.

In the rapidly evolving landscape of data sharing and stewardship, one of the major challenges is the building of trust both within and among diverse scientific communities. A major step forward in this respect was the development and publication of the 'WDS Data Sharing Principles', which provide a clear statement of the core ethical commitments adopted by our Member Organizations and underpinning the process of WDS certification.

Dissemination of knowledge is also an important part of building trust within and among communities. WDS is taking an increasingly active role in community-building by providing Webinars on a variety of data topics. There have been nine such Webinars since October 2014, with more planned in the future that draw on the strengths and interests of our Members. Workshops also provide a way of reaching out to the wider community, and WDS has organized outreach workshops at

important international conferences such as *Our Common Future Under Climate Change* (July 2015, Paris), and at key society meetings such as AGU and EGU. In addition, WDS worked with its Member Organizations on more specific data-focussed workshops: Global Data Activities for the Research of Solar–Terrestrial Variability (September 2015, Tokyo) and Polar Data Forum II (October 2015, Waterloo).

Early career researchers are enthusiastic adopters of data sharing and have an important part to play in the promotion and development of good practices for data stewardship. The WDS Data Stewardship Award was created to acknowledge this important role. The 2015 Award was given to Dr Yaxing Wei of ORNL DAAC in recognition of his innovative work on data documentation and visualization—which has led to a major increase in the usage and distribution of geospatial data archived at the DAAC. Dr Wei will receive his award alongside Dr Boris Biskaborn, the 2016 Award winner, at SciDataCon 2016 this September.

Sandy P. Harrison
Chair, WDS-SC

Activities in Priority Areas

SCOSTEP–WDS Workshop on Global Data Activities
for the Research of Solar–Terrestrial Variability

WDS Webinars

WDS Data Stewardship Award 2015

Polar Data Forum II

WDS Working Groups

Links with Partners

SCOSTEP–WDS Workshop on Global Data Activities for the Research of Solar–Terrestrial Variability

On 28–30 September 2015, a joint Workshop was held at the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology in Tokyo between the ICSU World Data System and the ICSU Scientific Committee on Solar–Terrestrial Physics (SCOSTEP). In total, 51 papers were presented, over half of which dealt with data-oriented activities, while many of the remaining papers discussed solar–terrestrial phenomena on various timescales, such as the so-called 2015 Saint Patrick's Day Event. A number of extended papers from Workshop

will be published in a special issue of the *Earth, Planets and Space* journal.

A predominant outcome of the Workshop was the signing of a Letter of Agreement between the two organizations as an initial step in collaborating on the data activities of the Variability of the Sun and Its Terrestrial Impact programme (VarSITI; see below).

SCOSTEP Becomes WDS Partner Member

During the SCOSTEP–WDS Workshop, Dr Nat Gopalswamy (President of ICSU-SCOSTEP) and Dr Mustapha Mokrane (Executive Director of ICSU-WDS) signed a Letter of Agreement recognizing SCOSTEP as a WDS Partner Member. This formal arrangement strengthens the ongoing collaborations between the two bodies, in particular those dealing with data challenges and opportunities of the VarSITI programme. It also allows SCOSTEP to formally participate in WDS Members' Fora, while WDS becomes a SCOSTEP Bureau Member.

WDS Webinars

The WDS Scientific Committee launched the WDS Webinar series in mid-2013 as a platform for community building and networking through (virtual) workshops. Since then, both WDS Members and external data experts have been invited as guest speakers to host short talks on data topics of wide interest to the community.

After a measured start, the WDS Webinar series really gathered momentum in 2015–2016, with a number of excellent presentations and presenters not only building up synergies amongst an audience increasing in number and diversity, but also garnering a lot of positive feedback in the process. Below is a brief overview of all of the Webinars hosted by the WDS International Programme Office between April 2015 and March 2016.

Webinar #4: Combining High Performance Computing with High Performance Data to Enable Data Intensive Science

On 22 April 2015, Dr Lesley Wyborn presented experiences and lessons learned at the National Computational Infrastructure of the Australian National University to manage and make major research data collections discoverable and interoperable.

Webinar #5: BIGDATA, littledata and EvErYtHiNg in Between

Dr John Helly presented the fifth WDS Webinar on 10 June 2015; exploring the requirements on scientific data management not only resulting from research methods but also evolving from scholarly data publication. The technologies employed to satisfy these requirements have implications for any reasoned implementation of a scientific data management strategy.

Webinar #6: Web-centric Solutions for Web-based Scholarship

On 23 July 2015, Dr Herbert Van de Sompel presented WDS Webinar #6 on the perspectives he has gained over the past fifteen years spent tackling information interoperability problems for web-based scholarship. In this talk, he illustrated the shift from a repository- to web-centric approach by means of design patterns from various interoperability efforts, including Open Annotation, Memento, ResourceSync, Signposting the Scholarly Web, and Robust Links.

Webinar #7: Historical Seismograms: Preserving an Endangered Species

A review of the nature of the datasets in seismological archives and of the specific algorithms allowing their use was presented by Prof Emile Okal on 6 November 2015. He described the protocols for transferring analogue datasets to digital supports, and gave examples of existing collections and of successful digital archiving programmes of valuable datasets.

Webinar #8: Crowdsourcing Data and Quality Control—The Experience of OpenStreetMap

OpenStreetMap is the largest effort to harness the power of the Internet for crowd-sourced spatial data generation, with greater than 2.3m registered users helping to map over 34m km of roads in all countries.

On 10 February 2016, Mikel Maron and Paola Kim-Blanco presented on the necessary and specific efforts undertaken to ensure the quality and accuracy of member contributions.

WDS Data Stewardship Award 2015

Congratulations to Dr Yaxing Wei of Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center (ORNL DAAC; WDS Regular Member), who was selected by the WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC) from a strong list of candidates as the winner of the WDS Data Stewardship Award for 2015. This accolade highlights exceptional contributions to the improvement of scientific data stewardship by early career researchers through their engagement with the community, academic achievements, and innovations. The information and endorsements supplied by ORNL DAAC demonstrated to the WDS-SC that Dr Wei was a worthy recipient of the 2015 Award, which will be presented at SciDataCon 2016.

Dr Yaxing Wei is a geospatial information scientist who has demonstrated many exceptional contributions to scientific data stewardship in the Environmental and Global Climate Change Sciences. Dr Wei leads several tasks related to data standardization, integration, documentation, and management support for data informatics projects funded by National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE), and the National Science Foundation.

At ORNL DAAC, one of NASA's data archival centres, Dr Wei is responsible for the curation and quality assurance of Environmental Sciences data, and is leading research and development of interoperability and standards-based data analysis, visualization, and distribution for cyberinfrastructure in the centre. Through his innovative data tools, the geospatial data usage and distribution of ORNL DAAC archived datasets have increased many-fold.

Since 2008, Dr Wei has provided dedicated data management support for numerous climate change research projects. An example is the Multiscale Synthesis and Terrestrial Model Intercomparison Project of the North American Carbon Program (NACP), in which his significant contributions to data stewardship have facilitated scientific understanding and discoveries about the carbon cycle and climate change

on global and continental scales. In this regard, Dr Wei is a key member of the terrestrial ecology community, where his interactions through ORNL DAAC and NACP are vital for addressing the data archiving and distribution needs of diverse data products.

Dr Wei also has scientific data stewardship activities in the area of renewable energy. He is directly involved in the development of Hydro Data Infrastructure for the DOE-funded National Hydropower Assets and Resources Assessment Project. In particular, he is spearheading an effort to create a web-based geospatial system to visualize the hydropower potential within the U.S. by assessing the current value of hydroelectric infrastructure, quantifying the amounts of energy that could be feasibly extracted, and providing an environmental attribution resource for the DOE Water Power Program.

Polar Data Forum II: International Collaboration for Advancing Polar Data Access and Preservation

Greater than 110 people gathered to address the technical, social, policy, and economic challenges around polar data management at the Second International Polar Data Forum (27–29 October; Waterloo). Co-organized by ICSU-WDS, Polar Data Forum II brought together data managers, scientists, funding programme managers, indigenous people and their representatives, students, and others from eighteen nations to share their knowledge, experience, and ideas on how to make polar data more valuable in the quest to solve global problems.

Polar Data Forum I—the WDS co-hosted International Forum on ‘Polar Data Activities in Global Data Systems’ (15–16 October 2013; Tokyo)—saw the community identifying issues and making observations and recommendations on polar

data management. It focussed on improving how people and systems can share data in a meaningful way, with the goal of moving towards open and connected systems based on a culture of trust and acknowledgement of data production and use.

Polar Data Forum II highlighted the significant progress made in polar data management following the first Forum; pinpointing priorities to continue the resulting forward momentum gained in its aftermath. In this regard, the community reconfirmed the themes of Polar Data Forum I, but also identified key new themes that have evolved since then and recorded a new set of action-oriented recommendations and planned activities in a Communiqué (available at www.polar-data-forum.org).

WDS Working Groups

Publishing Data

Four Working Groups (WGs)—Bibliometrics, Cost Recovery, Services, and Workflows—were established under an umbrella Publishing Data WG by ICSU-WDS in 2012 (and later endorsed by the Research Data Alliance [RDA]) to address essential and practical issues in order to help enable the publication of research data as part of the scholarly record. The overarching objective of these WGs was to identify and define best practices for publishing data and to test their implementation across the core stakeholders involved: researchers and their institutions, data centres, scholarly publishers, and research funders.

After approximately two years of activities, the outputs of the WGs, which were developed by and in consultation with a broad representation of relevant stakeholders, are now available. The results are promising; especially, one of the overall developments has been the indication that data publishing procedures will increasingly conform to the model elaborated by the Workflows WG. The expectation is thus that there will be wider adoption of citation/referencing practices in scholarly publishing, which in turn raises the need for effective metadata services enabling bibliometric evaluation of research performance, as well as enhanced data discovery. A particular focus for the future will be to continue to develop the current Data–Literature Interlinking Service into a discovery service for data publications. The Service already has a number of endorsers, which is essential for its further development.

Bibliometrics

Applying citation counts to data as an indicator of quality is problematic, firstly because the culture of data citation is not yet ingrained in scientific communities, and secondly because the notion of data quality itself is extremely difficult to define. Moreover, treating datasets as fixed, complete objects in order to use current citation count mechanisms limits the range and types of data that can be measured in this way. A mechanism is hence needed for evaluating the impact of a dataset across multiple categories of stakeholders; one that is easy to use and that can compare datasets for ranking purposes, whilst avoiding the 'gamification' of any new metrics.

The aim of the Bibliometrics WG was to conceptualize data metrics and corresponding services that are suitable to overcome existing barriers in data quality, with the outcome to initiate a cultural change among scientists: encouraging more and better data citations, increasing the overall availability and quality of research data, enhancing data discoverability and reuse, and facilitating the reproducibility of research results.

To achieve its aim, the WG performed a survey that resulted in

a list of the metrics currently being collected by data services, in addition to a systematic overview of current major gaps and deficiencies in data bibliometrics. These results enabled the evaluation of the services supplied by a number of service providers, and explained why adoption of bibliometrics by science users and organizations is still only just beginning.

Data bibliometrics remain in their infancy and as such, implementation is still some way off from being mature enough for operational practices. Several teams are working on the development of the necessary components of data metrics, and their outputs when combined with those of the WG will advance understanding of the need for data bibliometrics, as well as driving adoption of the associated facets. Through such partnerships with other stakeholders, the WG's efforts will thus continue to be focussed on building a culture of assessment of data metrics grounded in consistent data collection.

Cost Recovery

The goals of this WG were to improve understanding of how data services are presently funded and their practices of cost recovery, and to identify possible opportunities for services looking to diversify their income streams. These goals are a necessary precondition for identifying sustainable business models.

To sample the funding landscape, the WG conducted in-depth interviews with 25 data services worldwide; designed to examine current business models and any new income streams being trialled/considered, as well as to assess attitudes to funding diversification and to sustainability. The survey results were used to ascertain the most prevalent business models and to perform a Strengths–Weaknesses–Opportunities–Threats analysis. These findings, augmented with preliminary conclusions and recommendations for further work, were then incorporated into a final report.

The major findings of the survey were:

- Funding budgets, instruments, and procedures vary widely across data services and national funding systems.
- Funding appears to be determined and allocated on a per-initiative basis, with considerable variety in approach. Funding horizons are relatively short, and budgets are substantially augmented by short-term, project-based funding.
- The sustainability and adequacy of funding is a matter of concern and there are many unsolved issues.
- Structural funding suits many data services, as long as they can be certain of long-term commitment by the funder and there are mechanisms in place to ensure that the service can evolve as required.
- Data access charges are at odds with current policy requirements, whilst charging for value-added services is

recognized but underexploited.

- Although consistent with Open Access and potentially scalable, data deposit fees are being explored in only a limited way since there are concerns about administrative overheads and negative market effects.
- Project funding can be an essential additional source of income. However, repositories do not want to rely on short-term project funding for long-term core activities.
- Stakeholders must carefully consider what proportion of data infrastructure should be supported by short-term grants, and this needs to be tested.

These results provide data infrastructure stakeholders useful insights into the opportunities available to diversify income streams and to develop sustainable business models that are sufficiently elastic to meet new and growing data needs. Nevertheless, two areas need more attention:

- Relatively few innovative income streams were identified by the data services interviewed, and in future work, business experts also need to be consulted.
- The means by which data services may reduce—or at least restrain—increasing costs.

This study was the first step towards a more detailed analysis of sustainable business models. An important outcome is thus the initiation of a 18-month project in March 2016 under the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development – Global Science Forum (see 'Links with Partners'), which will build directly on the outputs of the WG and will ultimately make policy recommendations to promote more sustainable business models for supporting data (publishing) infrastructure.

Services

The visibility of both data and publications is increased by creating bi-directional links between them, and data can be interpreted in the right context much more easily. However, the organizations that track and expose such links usually do so alone through bilateral arrangements, resulting in isolated collections of links that limit their value and usefulness for researchers.

The objective of the Services WG was to establish an open, universal, one-for-all service that collects, harmonizes, and exposes links between data and literature by creating workflows for participating organizations to share their links; casting them into a common interoperable format and building the infrastructure needed to aggregate and expose them. Its key output has been the realization of the principles and prototype for a *Data–Literature Interlinking (DLI) Service*, developed in a synergistic effort with OpenAIRE and PANGAEA (WDS Regular Member). This service is based on over two million article/data links collected from various sources, and offers a web portal and the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting to expose the links. It also powers application programming interfaces (APIs) that can be used to query the system automatically, facilitating adoption on live platforms. By building on the substantial support given by all relevant stakeholders, it is expected that the Service will be operational by autumn 2016.

The WG has additionally delivered a set of recommendations on how to evolve the DLI into a sustainable, robust service for all stakeholders—including a technical architecture, governance model, and adoption plan. To that end, a workshop was organized with major stakeholders to form a common consensus on the infrastructural model needed to

support the operation of a sustainable DLI, building largely on existing infrastructure. CrossRef, DataCite (WDS Partner Member), and OpenAIRE have committed to intensify their collaboration and to work with the wider community in order to define a common standard for describing and exchanging links between data and the literature. As a first step, CrossRef and OpenAIRE are currently exploring how information can be pushed from the DLI into CrossRef’s Digital Object Identifier Event Tracker.

Other examples of implementation and adoption of the WG’s outputs include:

- Europe PMC adopting the metadata standards developed by the WG to describe article/data links in its system. The DLI can then harvest these links for inclusion in the service.
- The ‘RD-switchboard’ developed by the RDA Data Description Registry Interoperability WG ingesting links from the DLI to combine with other content sources and improve their services.
- CHORUS requesting an overview of datasets linked to the articles it holds.
- Several data services investigating how to connect with the DLI via an API to offer a ‘related publications’ functionality to users of their web portals.

Workflows

Different components of a data publishing system need to be interoperable and accessible in a seamless way. The Workflows WG analyzed a diverse range of workflows from data publication stakeholders to identify common components and standard practices. Workflows were characterized by discipline, function, data formats, and roles involved, as well as ten characteristics associated with data publishing. The findings from this survey were then used to derive a data publishing reference model comprised of generic components. Recommendations resulting from the WG are to:

- Implement effective and trustworthy practices for all parts of a (documented) data publishing workflow, as well as developing new procedures where necessary.
- Start small and build components one-by-one in a modular way with a good understanding of how each building block fits into the overall workflow and what the final objective is. Ideally, these building blocks should be open source/shareable components.
- Follow (disciplinary, community-endorsed) standards whenever available to facilitate interoperability and to permit extensions based on the work of others using the same standards.
- Implement and adhere to standards for data citation, including the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) to establish connections between entities (data, publications, researchers, software, etc.), and thus facilitate automatic harvesting. The use of PIDs can also enable linked open data functionality.
- Document roles, workflows, and services. A key difficulty in conducting the workflow analysis was the lack of complete, standardized, and up-to-date information about the processes and services provided by the platforms themselves. This

impacts potential users of the services as well.

With the analysis leading to a model based on established workflows and best practices components, this enables easier implementation than is typical for such reference models. Many organizations engaged in data publication have thus already adopted and are employing elements of the reference model. The Digital Curation Centre, in particular, is drawing on the reference model in its 'How to Document Workflows for Data Preservation and Publishing' guide (to be published in 2016), setting out the benefits of workflow documentation, describing simple tools for doing so, and illustrating examples that build on the WG's report.

Inclusion of term definitions used in recognized glossaries will be a positive forward step for the reference model since it will create a common language wherein its understanding is improved and it can be further developed. Moreover, the public release of the model intends to make it available for relevance testing, community review, and amendment; and it will continue to be sustained and advanced by the broader data publication community—if found to be relevant and adaptable—as available technologies and practices in data publication progress.

Certification

The ICSU World Data System and the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) both offer core certification standards for trustworthy digital repositories across all of the Sciences. Applicants to ICSU-WDS and DSA generally see these certifications as beneficial, since not only do they support trust in a digital repository, they also stimulate it to improve its processes and procedures and to move to a higher level of professionalism, with an incentive to enhance its operations over time. However, whilst the catalogues of criteria and review procedures of both organizations are based on the same principles of openness and transparency, and of striking a balance between simplicity and robustness of the work and effort involved, the two standards have evolved and operated independently.

Since its inception in 2012 (later endorsed by RDA), the Certification WG—consisting of representatives from both organizations' communities—has explored and developed a DSA–WDS Partnership with the objectives of realizing efficiencies, simplifying assessment options, stimulating more certifications, and increasing impact on the community. Its outputs have been a harmonized Catalogue of Common Requirements for core certification of digital repositories that is drawn from the DSA and WDS catalogues of criteria, as well as a set of Common Procedures to implement the DSA–WDS Certification. Hence, the two organizations have developed a unified Common Certification Standard based on a side-by-side analysis of their present certification frameworks. These new Common Requirements and (to some extent) Procedures have been validated through a testbed comprised of DSA and WDS community members undergoing renewal of their certifications, with the results to be published in short report in mid-2016.

The proposed Common Certification Standard will be implemented by the two organizations, and integrated into their tools and systems, before the end of 2016. The greatest impact of this work is that it is a step towards having more coherent, increasingly stringent, and compatible standards for digital repository certification. Although ICSU-WDS and DSA will still take into account the different emphasises of their systems in the initial stages, the barriers between their certifications will be significantly lowered, and it is expected that the Common Certification Standard will be boosted in its adoption by creating a critical mass of certified digital repositories. Already certified digital repositories will transition to the new DSA–WDS Common Requirements as they renew their certifications, with an eventual goal being that accreditation through either organization will mean the digital repository is certified by the other; eliminating duplication of effort.

Links with Partners

International Council for Science

The World Data System hosted a successful session and side event at *Our Common Future under Climate Change* (6–10 July; Paris)—the premier international climate science conference organized by a partnership of French and international institutions (including the International Council for Science [ICSU]) that took place ahead of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change 21st Conference of the Parties (COP21) held in December 2015 in Paris.

WDS also released a Position Statement for the side-event ‘Science and the Road to Transformation: Opportunities in the post-2015 Global Climate Regime’ organized by ICSU ahead of the conference.

Science International Launches Campaign for ‘Open Data in a Big Data World’

Four of the major international science organizations—ICSU, International Social Science Council, InterAcademy Partnership, and The World Academy of Sciences—have come together to develop and support an Accord on ‘Open Data in a Big Data World’. The ICSU Committee on Data for Science and Technology and ICSU-WDS played a role in the creation of the Accord, which includes a set of guiding principles on open access to Big Data that necessarily protects the scientific process and ensures that developing countries can participate more fully in the global research enterprise. For the 12 months following the launch of the document, the campaign will look to collect endorsements for the Accord from other science, education, and policy bodies, with final results anticipated in the third-quarter of 2016.

Research Data Alliance

ICSU-WDS was strongly involved in the activities of the 6th and 7th Plenary Meetings of the Research Data Alliance (RDA). These Meetings are built around sessions organized by RDA Interest and Working Groups (IGs and WGs), which are now beginning to release their outputs and to promote adoption and success stories.

The theme of the 6th Plenary Meeting (23–25 September 2015; Paris) was Enterprise Engagement with a focus on Research Data for Climate Change, leveraging on COP21. Its programme contained sessions in which the RDA–WDS IGs and WGs on both Publishing Data and Certification communicated their initial outputs to the Plenary. In particular, the former showcased its prototype Data–Literature Interlinking Service, and the latter presented its set of Common Requirements and Procedures.

The 7th Plenary (1–3 March 2016; Tokyo) was the first RDA

meeting to be held in Asia. Beyond the convenience of being located on its doorstep, the WDS International Programme Office organized and contributed to several key events:

- A *Publishing Data: Adoption and Implementation* side-event before the Meeting on behalf of the WDS–RDA Publishing Data IG, in cooperation with the International Association of STM Publishers (WDS Associate Member) and the US National Information Standards Organization.
- Presentations during the Plenary Meeting by the joint RDA–WDS Publishing Data IGs and WGs and the DSA–WDS Partnership WG on their final outputs and the adoption of these.
- A further WDS side-event after the Meeting entitled *Data Perspective beyond Alliances* that highlighted two projects under the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development – Global Science Forum (see below).

Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) released its report in 2015 on 'Making Open Science a Reality' for which the ICSU Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA) and ICSU-WDS were consulted at a number of points.

The ICSU organizations have also initiated two activities together with OECD's Global Science Forum (OECD-GSF) concerned with

- *Sustainable Business Models for Data Repositories* that will be led by ICSU-CODATA and that will gain funding to follow up and develop on the work of the RDA-WDS Cost Recovery IG.
- *International Coordination of Data Infrastructures* that is a new activity led by ICSU-WDS and that is linked with its Strategic Target #3: Improve the funding environment.

The proposals for both activities have been approved by OECD-GSF, and will run for 12–15 months from April 2016. Moreover, the three partners have assembled experts groups that will support the activities, with the outputs expected to be positive, concrete policy recommendations for sustainable data infrastructures.

Institute of Geographic Science and Natural Resources Research

On 10–29 August 2015, 29 trainees from 9 countries (Bangladesh, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Pakistan, Russian Federation, Tajikistan, Thailand, and Uzbekistan) attended the 'International Workshop on Northeast Asia–Central Asia Regional Resources and Environment Data Sharing'. Held in Beijing, China by the Institute of Geographic Science and Natural Resources Research (IGSNRR), the workshop was co-sponsored by the ICSU World Data System and the World Data Centre for Renewable Resources and Environment (WDS Regular Member).

Training throughout the workshop was set in a multidisciplinary context, and addressed a broad range of scientific data-sharing issues from national, regional, and international perspectives, including policies, standards, technologies, methods, and good practices. On the final day, Mustapha Mokrane (WDS Executive Director) gave a lecture on the development of ICSU-WDS and the global data-sharing landscape.

Group on Earth Observations

Mustapha Mokrane represented ICSU-WDS—as a participating organization of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO)—at GEO’s 12th Plenary on 11–13 November in Mexico City. WDS’ declaration stated its wish to continue contributing to GEO activities such as being part the Task Force generating Implementation Guidelines for the GEO Data Management Principles, which are currently being refined after having been submitted to the Plenary, and for which ICSU-WDS submitted content and led on some of the sections. Since GEO is now reaching the point of realizing the Guidelines, ICSU-WDS also offered its certification framework as a method for doing that. One of the main outcomes of the Plenary from a WDS perspective was that Arona Diedhiou of the WDS Scientific Committee was appointed to the GEO Programme Board that guides the future developments of GEO under the supervision of its Executive Committee.

Future Earth

ICSU-WDS continued its engagement with Future Earth (FE) on data issues by organizing two meetings in 2015 with the nascent FE Data and Information and Observations Task Force: the first taking advantage of everyone’s presence at the GEO Plenary (10 November 2015; Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Mexico City), and the second back-to-back with a number of other FE meetings taking place in Japan (18 November 2015; Science Council of Japan, Tokyo).

At the second meeting, the FE Science Committee officially recognized the Task Force within the structure of Future Earth, and formally appointed its two co-chairs—Dr Eduardo Brondizio (FE Science Committee) and Mr Mario Hernandez (FE Engagement Committee). The activities of this Task Force are thus now gaining momentum.

Administration & Governance

New WDS Data Sharing Principles

2015–2018 Chair and Scientific Committee Appointed

Hosting Agreement Renewed for WDS-IPO

WDS Scientific Committee

WDS Members

WDS International Programme Office

New WDS Data Sharing Principles

As the leading international, multidisciplinary organization in the provision of trusted data services, the International Council for Science – World Data System has adopted a new set of Data Sharing Principles to advance its goals and to embody the spirit of ‘Open Science’ meant to unite the diverse communities of data producers and users.

The Principles are in line with the data policies of many national and international initiatives, and they express the core ethical commitments that are operationalized through the WDS certification and with which the existing organizational policies of WDS Members are expected to be aligned.

The first draft of the Principles was developed by the WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC), who then initiated a full consultation with WDS Member Organizations. We would like to acknowledge and to thank WDS Members for their overwhelming support for the draft version and for all of the positive feedback. Their valuable contributions were incorporated by the WDS-SC into the final version of the Principles, which have been placed on the WDS website and can also be found on ZENODO (DOI:10.5281/zenodo.34354) as part of the WDS Community Collection.

Principles

- Data, metadata, products, and information should be fully and openly shared, subject to national or international jurisdictional laws and policies, including respecting appropriate extant restrictions, and in accordance with international standards of ethical research conduct.
- Data, metadata, products, and information produced for research, education, and public-domain use will be made available with minimum time delay and free of charge, or for no more than the cost of dissemination, which may be waived for lower-income user communities to support equity in access.
- All who produce, share, and use data and metadata are stewards of those data, and have responsibility for ensuring that the authenticity, quality, and integrity of the data are preserved, and respect for the data source is maintained by ensuring privacy where appropriate, and encouraging appropriate citation of the dataset and original work and acknowledgement of the data repository.
- Data should be labelled ‘sensitive’ or ‘restricted’ only with appropriate justification and following clearly defined protocols, and should in any event be made available for use on the least restrictive basis possible.

2015–2018 Chair and Scientific Committee Appointed

Selected by the Executive Board of the International Council for Science (ICSU), the third Scientific Committee of the World Data System (WDS-SC) was appointed on 1 July 2015 for a three-year period. Sandy Harrison—who officially started her first term after joining the WDS-SC in May 2014—agreed to be the new SC Chair until 2017. Sandy is a Professor of Palaeoclimates and Biogeochemical Cycles, and took over the role of Chair from Professor Bernard Minster, whose term was exceptionally extended for one additional SC Meeting to enable a formal handover of the leadership. In this regard, ICSU has introduced a stagger between the appointment of the SC Chair and members to ensure leadership continuity in the future.

At the time of its appointment, the WDS-SC contained eight new members, taking into account that at least one-third of the Committee are directors of WDS Member Organizations. With

a lack of representation from the Latin America and Caribbean region, however, the Executive Board approved that a vacant thirteenth seat be made available to foster geographical balance. This seat was then filled in December 2015 by Alfredo Tolmasquim. Moreover, with Rob Kitchin resigning from the WDS-SC in autumn 2015, Isabelle Gärtner-Roer was also invited by the ICSU Executive Board to serve on the WDS-SC in December.

The new Scientific Committee and the WDS International Programme Office sincerely thank all of the outgoing SC members for their dedication to ICSU-WDS. Especially to Michael Diepenbroek, Françoise Genova, Ruth Neilan, and Lesley Rickards, who were on the very first Scientific Committee and who have been involved with ICSU-WDS for the past six years.

Hosting Agreement Renewed for WDS-IPO

Dr Fumihiko Tomita, Vice President of the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT), and Dr Heide Hackmann, Executive Director of the International Council for Science (ICSU), renewed the agreement between their respective organizations to host the WDS International Programme Office at NICT in Tokyo, Japan for a further five-year period starting 1 April 2016.

The signing ceremony took place on 21 September 2015 at the ICSU Secretariat in Paris, during the 13th Meeting of the WDS Scientific Committee. At the ceremony, Dr Hackmann expressed her sincere thanks to NICT on behalf of ICSU and WDS for its generous financial support, and noted that without NICT's lasting commitment and intellectual contributions, ICSU-WDS could not have achieved either its current international standing or its significant impact in the area of scientific data sharing and management.

WDS Scientific Committee

ICSU-WDS is governed by a Scientific Committee (the WDS-SC) composed of prominent scientists actively involved in Data/Computer Sciences, and dealing with large dataset issues and long-term data stewardship. The WDS-SC includes directors of WDS Member Organizations and covers a broad range of disciplines and geographical areas.

Chair

Sandy Harrison: Centre for Past Climate Change, University of Reading, United Kingdom / Macquarie University, Australia

Vice-chairs

Ingrid Dillo: Data Archiving and Networked Services, The Netherlands

Wim Hugo: South African Earth Observation System, South Africa

Members

Aude Chambodut: Ecole et Observatoire des Sciences de la Terre, France

Alex de Sherbinin: Center for International Earth Science Information Network, University of Columbia, USA

Arona Diedhiou: Institute of Research for Development and Laboratoire d'Etude des Transferts en Hydrologie et Environnement, University of Grenoble-Alpes, France / Laboratoire de Physique de l'Atmosphère et Mécanique des fluides, Université Félix Houphouët Boigny, Côte d'Ivoire

Claudia Emerson: Department of Philosophy, McMaster University, Canada

Elaine Faustman: Institute for Risk Analyses and Risk Communication, University of Washington, Seattle, USA

Isabelle Gärtner-Roer: Department of Geography, University of Zurich, Switzerland

Toshihiko Iyemori: Data Analysis Center for Geomagnetism and Space Magnetism, Kyoto University, Japan.

Guoqing Li: Institute of Remote Sensing and Digital Earth, China

Sanna Sorvari: Finnish Meteorological Institute, Helsinki, Finland

Alfredo Tolmasquim: Museum of Astronomy and Related Sciences, History of Science Coordination, Brazil

Ex Officio Members

Heide Hackmann: International Council for Science

Yasuhiro Murayama: National Institute of Information and Communications Technology, Japan

Thirteenth WDS Scientific Committee Meeting

The 13th Meeting of the WDS-SC took place on 21–22 September at the International Council for Science (ICSU) Secretariat in Paris, France. This was the first face-to-face meeting of the Third Scientific Committee, which was marked with a (virtual) handover from the previous Chair of the WDS-SC, Bernard Minster, to the new Chair, Sandy Harrison.

Heide Hackmann (ICSU Executive Director) commenced a half-day series of introductory talks on ICSU and WDS by giving the new Committee an insight into ICSU's vision and the role of WDS within this. The agenda then continued over the following day-and-a-half with focussed discussions on items of strategic importance to ICSU-WDS, including finalizing the WDS Data Sharing Principles.

The first day of the Meeting ended with a special Workshop by the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT) on 'Data Sharing and Information Communications Technology', the highlight of which was a keynote presentation by Fumihiko Tomita (NICT Vice President) on *Open and Global ICT Innovation Platform for Future Smarter Communication World*.

SC Members Post Monthly Blog Entries on WDS Website

In addition to news articles, the WDS website points to articles/information of interest in the WDS Blog. To increase communication and in the lead up to SciDataCon 2016, the WDS-SC decided that its members would introduce themselves each month by writing a short Blog entry on a topic they are currently involved with.

The inaugural post was by Ingrid Dillo, Vice-chair of the WDS-SC, who in November 2015 introduced the new, open-access *Research Data Journal for the Humanities and Social Sciences* that was jointly launched by Data Archiving and Networked Services (WDS Regular Member) in the Netherlands.

WDS Members

Member Organizations of ICSU-WDS from wide-ranging fields are the building blocks of a worldwide ‘community of excellence’ for scientific data. Not only do these Members participate in advancing WDS goals; their data holdings, services, and products are the cornerstone of the federated data system.

On 31 March 2016, ICSU-WDS had 95 Member Organizations in four different categories.

- 61 Regular Members:** Organizations that are data stewards and/or data analysis services.
- 10 Network Members:** Umbrella bodies representing groups of data stewardship organizations and/or data analysis services, some of which may or may not be WDS Regular Members. Usually serve as coordinating agents for nodes that have common characteristics and mostly common disciplines.
- 6 Partner Members:** Organizations that are not data stewards or data analysis services, but that contribute support or funding to ICSU-WDS and/or WDS Members.
- 18 Associate Members:** Organizations that are interested in the WDS endeavour and participating in our discussions, but that do not contribute direct funding or other material support.

Member Organizations are formally accepted into ICSU-WDS by the WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC), who safeguard the trustworthiness of ICSU-WDS by certifying Regular and Network Members according to internationally recognized standards (Partners and Associates are co-opted).

The following organizations were affiliated as WDS Members during fiscal year 2015.

WDC – RSER Transfers Data Holdings to WDC – Meteorology, Obninsk

The WDS-SC was pleased to learn that in spite of being closed down in 2015, the data holdings of WDC – Rockets, Satellites and Earth Rotation (WDC – RSER) became part of the collection of WDC – Meteorology, Obninsk (WDS Regular Member).

A tenet of ICSU-WDS is that Members find a mechanism to transfer their data activities if they can no longer continue their commitment to long-term data stewardship. That WDC – RSER’s data were moved to another host and continue to be openly accessible is a good lesson for others, and the WDS-SC hopes that all scientific data services—both WDS Members and beyond—will look to do likewise if faced with a similar situation in the future.

Regular Members

Organization Name	Host Institution(s)	Country
Data Archiving and Networked Services	Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences	Netherlands
National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Land Processes	United States Geological Survey	United States of America (USA)
NASA Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center	Center for International Earth Science Information Network	USA
Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level	National Oceanography Centre/Natural Environment Research Council	United Kingdom
Research Institute for Sustainable Humanosphere	Kyoto University	Japan
UNAVCO, Inc.	-	USA

Partner Members

Organization Name	Host Institution(s)	Country of Secretariat
Global Geodetic Observing System	German Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy	Germany
Scientific Committee On Solar Terrestrial Physics	Centre for Research in Earth and Space Science	Canada

The following organizations previously certified by the WDS-SC as Regular Members have regrettably had to resign their membership in 2015.

Organization Name	Date of Resignation)	Reason
WDC - Rockets, Satellites and Earth Rotation	24 October 2015	Closure due to change in interests by host institute
Tropical Ecology Assessment and Monitoring Network	03 November 2015	Severe staff limitations

WDS Members' Activity Reports 2013–2014

WDS Regular and Network Members are continuously evaluated by the WDS-SC and are required to produce a public Report of their activities according to a template. The initial round of reporting coincided with the 2014 WDS Members' Forum, and the Activity Reports for the period 2013–2014 were added to the WDS website after a review and feedback process by the WDS-SC. Along with promoting the key accomplishments and future goals of WDS Members to the community, these Reports will act as supporting documents when each Member undergoes its next cyclic review.

WDS International Programme Office

The WDS International Programme Office (WDS-IPO) coordinates the daily operations of ICSU-WDS and implements the decisions of the WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC). The IPO organizes the twice-yearly face-to-face meetings of the SC and the biennial WDS Conference, as well as conducting outreach and promotional activities.

Following a new agreement with International Council for Science (ICSU), the WDS-IPO will be hosted and financially supported until 31 March 2021 by the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT) in Tokyo, Japan.

Staff

Executive Director: Mustapha Mokrane

Senior Advisor: Takashi Watanabe

Programme Officer: Rorie Edmunds

Administrative Officer: Yuko Nikaido

Financial Summary

The main source of income for financing the WDS-IPO and its activities comes from the contributions of NICT, its host organization. In addition, ICSU supports the costs incurred for one of the WDS-SC's biannual meetings, which is typically held at the ICSU Secretariat in Paris, France.

The accounts of the WDS-IPO are maintained and audited by NICT, its host institute. The below statement of income and expenditure is for the period 1 April 2015 to 31 March 2016; corresponding to the Japanese fiscal year 2015.

Statement of Income and Expenditure

Income	Japanese Yen
2015 Contribution from NICT	¥31,000,000
NICT Special Contribution ¹	¥2,255,360
Total income	¥ 33,255,360
Expenditure	
Communication and Promotion	¥10,978,051
Administrative Support	¥15,688,126
Travel and Meeting Costs	¥5,215,352
Other Costs (Insurance, Bank Charges, etc.)	¥941,150
Equipment	¥232,597
Total Expenditure	¥33,055,276
Net (Income - Expenditure)	¥200,084

¹NICT compensated by covering part/all of specific expenses incurred. The WDS-SC and IPO staff thanks NICT for its generosity in granting this additional contribution to the IPO funds

The long-term
ICSU vision is for a world
where excellence in science is
effectively translated into policy making
and socio-economic development. In such
a world, universal and equitable access to
scientific data and information is a reality and
all countries have the scientific capacity to
use these and to contribute to generating
the new knowledge that is necessary to
establish their own development
pathways in a sustainable
manner.

WORLD DATA SYSTEM

IPO Host:

World Data System

International Programme Office (c/o NICT)

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